

Evaluating Scoring Models to Align with Proposed Cognitive Constructs Underlying Item Content

Validate Content related to Clinical Judgement and Item Design

VALIDATION & USABILITY

On-going Learning – Cognitive Labs

- Some Goals:
 - Provide evidence that:
 - New items measure the intended CJ construct
 - Design is easily understood & easy to use (intuitive use)
 - Identify any construct irrelevant features for re-factoring
 - Look for correspondence between SME intention and participant responses
 - Strategies employed to evaluate items
 - Thought process when engaging item
 - Does the participant express rationales for the item that correspond to the intended CJ element(s)
 - Evaluate the information search of participants with respect to CJ content stems and then evaluate the extent to which the response set matches their initial conceptualization
 - E.g., ask the stem without any expected responses, does participant expectation of what the item is suggesting match the SME expected response
- Think aloud protocols
 - Concurrent: used during real-time interaction
 - Retrospective: after interaction to provide reflective feedback

Validity Design Framework

Example: Concurrent Questions

1. *Tell me what you did to get your answer to this question.*

Probe as needed with: What in the question made you do that?

Exploring coding strategy (mark as many as apply):

- Used steps in Layer 2 of Clinical Judgement model (formed hypothesis, refined hypothesis, evaluated outcomes)
- Performed steps in Layer 3 of Forming Hypotheses (recognized cues, analyzed cues)
- Performed steps in Layer 3 of Refining Hypotheses (prioritize hypotheses, generate solutions)
- Performed steps in Layer 3 of Evaluation (take actions, evaluate outcomes)
- Discussed the following underlying clinical judgement concepts:

- Discussed the limitation of cues, hypotheses or evaluation
- Made an explicit reference to one or more of the related factors from Layer 4 (environment, medical records, patient observation, experience, specialty, cultural considerations, consequences and risks)
- Recalled prior knowledge. Describe: _____
- Relied on previous question [indicated item dependence]
- Other, describe: _____

Usability Studies

- Common elements:
 - Built in memorability design:
 - Evaluated immediate, intermediate, and long-term recall at each round
 - Same item format with different scenario, same scenario with different item format, and totally new items
 - All items viewed by at least 5 participants
 - All sessions saved (WebEx & videotape) for archive and review
- Wave 1:
 - 30 1st round participants reviewed items for design and cognitive features
 - 15 returned for a 2nd round & 8 returned for 3rd round
 - 70 items studied
- Wave 2:
 - 23 1st round participants reviewed items for design and cognitive features
 - 12 were returners from Wave 1 (used for long-term recall)
 - 15 returned for a 2nd round and 7 returned for 3rd round
 - 24 new items studied & 12 wave 1 items (both memorability and validate design)

Usability Studies Continued

- Some general findings:
 - Results support early design decisions
 - Feel the items are difficult, but navigable
 - Instruction sets were validated
 - Highlighting items have been tokenized: really like this functionality
 - Single- and multi-column layouts acceptable
 - Time moves left to right
 - Response types highly memorable & items only memorable for vague aspects of the content

Preliminary Approaches to Scoring

SCORING MODELS

Response Type: Multiple Response

- General Use Response Type
 - Similar to MC, but allows for multiple correct options
 - Instructions can induce different cognitive sets
 - ‘Select ALL ...’ vs. ‘Select N ...’ vs. ‘Select the top N ...’
- Allows for a wide range of constructs to be measured
 - Cue recognition, take action, identify risk clusters, evaluate outcomes
- Generally scored as right/wrong
 - Must select only the correct keys
 - Tend to be more difficult → similar to most difficult threshold in a GRM
- Explore polytomous scoring approaches

Examples

Read the following case study, then refer to the case study to answer the questions.

Time: 1300

The nurse is caring for a client who had surgery for a left femur fracture 24 hours ago. The client has an allergy to latex and has a ventriculoperitoneal shunt on the left side that was placed in infancy. A left long leg fiberglass cast was applied following surgery. The client received morphine intravenously one hour ago for incisional pain. Vital signs are: temperature 99.2° F (37.3° C), pulse 126, respirations 16, blood pressure 124/82, oxygen saturation 93%. The client is awake but irritable, and is shouting "Take this cast off!"

To perform a neurovascular assessment for the client, which of the following actions should the nurse take? Select all that apply.

- Palpate to determine the temperature of the left foot.
- Press down gently on the client's shoulders and ask the client to try to lift the shoulders.
- Palpate to determine the temperature of the left upper thigh.
- Check the client's pupils for reactivity to light.
- Check and compare the client's pedal pulses.
- Determine whether the client can wiggle the left toes.
- Note the color of the left foot.
- Ask the client, "Can you feel a squeeze of the toes on the left foot?"
- Determine how quickly color returns to the nailbed after the nurse squeezes the left great toe.
- Ask the client, "Can you tell me the current day and time?"
- Ask the client, "Can you tell me your name?"
- Ask the client, "Can you tell me where you are right now?"

Read the following case study, and then refer to the case study to answer the question.

The client is a 32-year-old, African American female who works as a high school teacher and was admitted to the hospital after reporting epigastric pain for 2 days. The client was diagnosed with cholecystitis and subsequently had an open cholecystectomy 24 hours ago. The client has a history of hypertension, a fractured humerus 15 months ago, and had chickenpox at 6 years of age. She is gravida 2, para 2. She exercises regularly by walking the family dog for 30 minutes daily. Her family history includes her father who had colon cancer and pulmonary tuberculosis, and her mother who has chronic renal failure and has had several transient ischemic attacks. The client denies smoking and drinks one glass of wine each day. She is allergic to sulfonamides and pollen. Current medications include metoprolol, norethindrone/ethinyl estradiol, and aspirin for headaches and muscle pain.

What are the factors that place this client at risk for developing a stroke?

Click to highlight the factors that place this client at risk for developing a stroke. Highlight only the risk factors for developing a stroke. To deselect a highlighted factor, click the factor again.

Read the case study below, then refer to the case study to answer the question.

The nurse is assessing a male client who has chronic renal failure and was admitted one day ago with bacterial pneumonia. The client's findings are listed below.

	Current	8 hours ago	24 hours ago
Blood pressure	136/84	138/86	134/82
Pulse	72	58	68
Respirations	16	14	12
Oral temperature	102.6° F (39.2° C)	100.3° F (37.9° C)	101.1° F (38.4° C)
Hemoglobin	11.5 g/dL (115 mmol/L)	12.8 g/dL (128 mmol/L)	13.5 g/dL (135 mmol/L)
Hematocrit	32 (0.32)	36 (0.36)	42 (0.42)
Platelet count	221,000/mm ³ (221 x 10 ⁹ /L)	223,400/mm ³ (223.4 x 10 ⁹ /L)	220,800/mm ³ (220.8 x 10 ⁹ /L)
White blood cell count	15,200/mm ³ (15.2 x 10 ⁹ /L)	15,300/mm ³ (15.3 x 10 ⁹ /L)	15,300/mm ³ (15.3 x 10 ⁹ /L)
Prothrombin time	12.1 seconds	12.2 seconds	12.3 seconds
Partial thromboplastin time	28 seconds	27 seconds	25 seconds
Serum potassium	5.3 mEq/L (5.3 mmol/L)	4.8 mEq/L (4.8 mmol/L)	4.5 mEq/L (4.5 mmol/L)
Serum sodium	142 mEq/L (142 mmol/L)	140 mEq/L (140 mmol/L)	143 mEq/L (143 mmol/L)
Blood urea nitrogen	52 mg/dL (18.6 mmol/L)	55 mg/dL (19.6 mmol/L)	51 mg/dL (18.2 mmol/L)
Serum creatinine	8.0 mg/dL (707.2 µmol/L)	8.2 mg/dL (724.9 µmol/L)	8.1 mg/dL (716.0 µmol/L)
Weight	210 lb (95.5 kg)	209 lb (95 kg)	206 lb (93.6 kg)
Edema	1+ pitting pedal	2+ pitting pedal	2+ pitting pedal
Urine output	23 mL/h	21 mL/h	24 mL/h

Which of the findings would be essential to follow up?

Click row(s) to highlight the finding(s) that would be essential to follow-up. Highlight only row(s) that require follow-up. To deselect a row, click the row again.

Read the following case study, then refer to the case study to answer the questions.

The nurse is caring for an 8-year-old client who experienced a cervical spinal cord injury four days ago and is receiving mechanical ventilation. The Progress Note is listed below.

Progress Notes

1410 The client received a nebulized bronchodilator treatment followed by chest physiotherapy and suctioning 15 minutes ago.

Which of the following findings should the nurse use to evaluate the effectiveness of the bronchodilator, suctioning and chest physiotherapy? Drag the four most important findings to the box on the right.

Findings

oxygen saturation level

arterial blood gas results

respiratory rate

presence of abdominal distention

chest x-ray results

respiratory effort

breath sounds

Four most important findings

Research Motivation

- Identify if additional information can be obtained from MR items
- Use of scoring methods beyond all correct/incorrect
 - Signal-detection theory (DeCarlo, 1998, 2011; Rouder & Lu, 2005)
 - Subsets of the correct answer set
 - True/False testlet model (Muntean & Betts, 2015)
- Evaluate methods for providing useful feedback to SME/CD
 - Traditional classical statistics might not be helpful